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ЗБЕРЕЖЕННЯ СІМЕЙНИХ ЗВ'ЯЗКІВ, ЯК КЛЮЧОВИЙ ЕЛЕМЕНТ РЕЗИЛЬЄНТНОСТІ РОДИН ВІЙСЬКОВОСЛУБОВЦІВ Матвієнко А.О., Мельник О.А.	402
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THE ROLE OF VAGAL REFLEXES IN INTENSIVE CARE

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Relevance. In recent years, the number of patients in Ukraine seeking help due to various paroxysmal conditions (panic attacks, vegetative crises, collapses, heart rhythm disturbances, etc.) has sharply increased. Additionally, many people, unfortunately, suffer multiple injuries due to mine-explosive trauma, and a qualified resuscitation specialist is not always nearby. Therefore, the correct and timely application of vagal reflexes, considering their influence on the cardiovascular and respiratory systems, which allows vital parameters to be corrected, may become a life-saving factor in treating many conditions. The use of vagus nerve stimulation methods affects many parameters, such as reducing heart rate, preventing arrhythmia attacks, positively influencing respiratory function, and even reducing systemic inflammation [1].

Objective of the study. To explore the potential of using vagus nerve stimulation in emergency care to improve the efficiency of managing and treating critical conditions in patients.

Materials and methods. Scientific databases and specialized works of researchers were reviewed and processed.

Results. Vagus nerve stimulation has gained wide recognition in medicine due to its multifaceted impact on various body systems, including cardiovascular, respiratory, and immune systems. Recent studies indicate that the vagus nerve can play a key role in regulating homeostasis in critical conditions, stabilizing patients' vital signs. According to Karemaker JM (2022), the vagus, due to its multifunctionality, goes far beyond just regulating heart rate (HR). Its influence on heart rate variability is just one of many functions that ensure an adequate response of the body to critical conditions [1].

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To influence the cardiovascular system more significantly, vagus stimulation through carotid sinus massage (a maneuver involving finger pressure on the carotid sinus and repeated massaging of the left or right carotid artery) is more effective.

In addition to stabilizing heart activity, vagus nerve stimulation also helps normalize respiratory function, which is especially important in emergency care for respiratory disturbances or distress. In a study by Zamotrinsky AV, Kondratiev B, and de Jong JW (2001), it was found that vagus stimulation in patients with coronary heart disease not only controls HR but also improves coronary circulation by enhancing sympathetic action, significantly reducing the risk of developing cardiac complications in emergencies, particularly improving the condition of patients with angina [2]. This confirms the potentially important use of vagal stimulation in patients with cardiovascular pathologies, especially in intensive care settings.

The experience of the COVID-19 pandemic provided an opportunity to discover new areas for the application of vagal stimulation. One of the most important discoveries was the potential to use vagus nerve stimulation to alleviate respiratory symptoms and inflammatory processes in patients with severe forms of COVID-19.

The vagus nerve, as is known, has a powerful anti-inflammatory effect through its activating influence on the "cholinergic anti-inflammatory pathway," thus affecting neuroimmunological reactions that control cytokine release. This reduces the levels of cytokines synthesized by interleukins-1 β (IL-1 β), interleukins-6 (IL-6), and/or tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α) or/and vascular endothelial adhesion molecules, decreasing systemic inflammation, which is critically important in severe cases of COVID-19 when a state such as a "cytokine storm" develops — an uncontrolled activation of cytokine-producing immune cells in the inflammation zone, releasing new portions of cytokines due to the direct connection between these two processes.

In a study by Seitz T, Bergmayr F, Kitzberger R, et al. (2023), a randomized controlled trial was conducted that demonstrated the use of vagal stimulation in patients with severe forms of COVID-19. Patients who received vagal stimulation through percutaneous stimulation of the auricular branch of the vagus nerve showed a reduced need for invasive lung ventilation [3]. This study underscores the importance of vagal stimulation in emergency situations where there is a need for quick and effective normalization of respiratory function and a reduction in the inflammatory burden on the body, particularly in conditions such as respiratory distress syndrome or multiple organ failure. The hypothetical cause of such complications is a disruption of the sympathovagal balance. Specifically, infection leads to an excessive reaction of the pro-inflammatory pathway of the sympathetic

nervous system, while the modulating anti-inflammatory pathway of the parasympathetic nervous system is impaired. Lung damage stimulates the sympathetic nervous system, leading to excessive release of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-6. This, in turn, triggers a cytokine cascade, with the cytokine storm causing pulmonary hemorrhage, edema, and atelectasis, leading to ARDS. Moreover, sympathovagal imbalance creates a state of severe hypoxemia and increases the risk of thrombotic or thromboembolic events, which can lead to acute myocardial injury and even chronic cardiovascular system damage. Thus, vagus stimulation can correct sympathovagal imbalance while simultaneously increasing the anti-inflammatory activity of the parasympathetic nervous system [3].

A comparison of different vagal stimulation methods shows that each has its own specifics and effectiveness depending on the pathology. The carotid reflex is most effective in managing patients with tachycardia and hypertensive crises, as its impact is almost instantaneous, quickly stabilizing the patient's condition. The Danini-Aschner reflex is significantly limited in intensive care due to the need for patient contact and the possible risk of excessive HR reduction, which can lead to hypotension. The solar reflex, in turn, has proven effective in treating vegetative disorders, but its use requires further research.

According to Karemaker (2022), the wide range of vagal responses and its ability to influence various body systems opens up new possibilities for treating various critical conditions [1]. Vagal stimulation, especially in the form of carotid massage and solar plexus stimulation, has shown high efficacy in stabilizing patients with critical conditions requiring intensive care.

Although vagal stimulation is an effective method in emergency care, it can cause a number of side effects depending on the method of stimulation, the patient's condition, and comorbidities.

One of the most common side effects of vagus nerve stimulation, especially during carotid sinus massage or the Danini-Aschner reflex, is a significant decrease in blood pressure. In patients with already low blood pressure or a tendency toward hypotension, this can lead to conditions such as fainting or hypotensive shock. Specifically, carotid sinus stimulation can overly activate the vagus nerve, causing excessive bradycardia and hypotension, which is especially dangerous in patients with atherosclerotic changes in the carotid arteries [1]. The vagus nerve significantly affects heart rate, so its stimulation often leads to a decrease in HR. This can be dangerous for patients whose initial heart rate is already low. Bradycardia can cause arrhythmia or even cardiac arrest if the stimulation is not properly controlled. This is especially true for the Danini-Aschner reflex and carotid massage [2]. A sharp decrease in HR and blood pressure can lead to insufficient blood supply to the brain, potentially causing loss of consciousness [4].

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Carotid sinus massage can lead to a temporary decrease in blood flow through the carotid arteries, which can cause a transient ischemic attack or even stroke in patients with atherosclerotic vascular lesions [4].

Vagus nerve stimulation can increase gastrointestinal activity, manifesting in symptoms such as nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, or spasms. This is due to enhanced parasympathetic innervation of the digestive organs [1].

Psychological side effects are particularly common in patients who undergo stimulation without prior psycho-emotional preparation [6].

Conclusions. Thus, the analysis of scientific works on this topic showed that vagus nerve stimulation is a promising method in emergency care for stabilizing cardiovascular and respiratory functions. Its application helps stabilize rhythm, reduce heart rate, lower blood pressure, and decrease systemic inflammation [1]. This is especially useful in intensive care for cardiovascular diseases [2] and the treatment of COVID-19 [3]. However, further research is needed to improve the effectiveness and safety of vagus stimulation [4, 5]. Possible side effects must also be considered [6].

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